

Solving the Cauchy problem for the extended fifth-order modified Korteweg-de Vries equation with an additional term and time-dependent coefficient

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Annotation. This article presents an algorithm for finding a solution to the Cauchy problem posed for the nonstationary fifth-order extended modified Korteweg-de Vries equation using the inverse problem method for the Dirac operator.

Key words. Modified Korteweg-de Vries equations, scattering data, Dirac operator, Gelfand-Levitan-Marchenko integral equations.

This article about as a fifth-order extended mKdV equation with time-dependent coefficients and an additional nonlinear term. Specifically, the following equation is analyzed:

$$u_t + 6u^2u_x + u_{xxx} + q(t)(30u^4u_x + 10u_x^3 + 40uu_xu_{xx} + 10u^2u_{xxx} + u_{xxxxx}) + s(t)u_x = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $q(t)$ and $s(t)$ are continuously differentiable prescribed functions.

Equation (1) is investigated under the initial condition

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x) \quad (2)$$

where the function $u_0(x)$ ($-\infty < x < \infty$) satisfies the following criteria:

$$1. \quad |u_0(x)|e^{2\varepsilon|x|} \leq \frac{\sigma}{(1+|x|)^{1+\zeta}}, \quad (3)$$

for positive constants $\varepsilon > 0$, $\zeta > 0$, and $\sigma > 0$.

$$2. \text{ The Dirac-type operator } L(0) = i \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d}{dx} & -u_0(x) \\ -u_0(x) & -\frac{d}{dx} \end{pmatrix} \text{ possesses exactly } N \text{ simple}$$

eigenvalues $c_1(0), c_2(0), \dots, c_N(0)$ in the upper half-plane and lacks spectral singularities.

The solution $u(x, t)$ is assumed to exhibit sufficient smoothness and sufficiently rapid decay as $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$, quantified by the condition:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{2\varepsilon|x|} \left(\sum_{k=0}^5 \left| \frac{\partial^k u(x, t)}{\partial x^k} \right| \right) dx < \infty. \quad (4)$$

The central aim of this work is to derive explicit representations for the solution $u(x,t)$ of the problem (1)-(4) using the inverse scattering transform (IST) framework applied to the time-dependent Dirac operator

$$\mathbf{L}(t) = i \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d}{dx} & -u(x,t) \\ -u(x,t) & -\frac{d}{dx} \end{pmatrix}.$$

In addition, the algorithms for solving the Cauchy problem for nonlinear evolutionary equations in the class of periodic and rapidly decreasing functions have been extensively studied in papers [1]–[10].

Thus, we have proved the following theorem.

Theorem 3. If the functions $u(x,t)$ are a solution to the problem (1)-(4), then the scattering data of the operator $\mathbf{L}(t)$ with the potential $u(x,t)$ vary with t as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathbf{c}_n}{dt} = 0, n = \overline{1, N}; \quad \frac{dr^+(\mathbf{c}, t)}{dt} &= (-32i\mathbf{c}^5\mathbf{q}(t) + 8i\mathbf{c}^3 - 2i\mathbf{c}\mathbf{s}(t))r^+(\mathbf{c}, t), \quad \text{Im } \mathbf{c} = 0; \\ \frac{d\mathbf{C}_n}{dt} &= (-32i\mathbf{c}_n^5\mathbf{q}(t) + 8i\mathbf{c}_n^3 - 2i\mathbf{c}_n\mathbf{s}(t))\mathbf{C}_n(t). \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1. The resulting set $\{r^+(\mathbf{c}, t), \mathbf{c}_j(t), \mathbf{C}_j(t), j = \overline{1, N}\}$ satisfies the conditions of Theorem 1, so according to Theorem 1 and 2, the potential $u(x,t)$ in the operator $\mathbf{L}(t)$ is uniquely determined and is a solution of problem (1)-(4). The behavior of the scattering data for the operator $\mathbf{L}(t)$ is entirely determined by the equations obtained in Theorem 3, which lays a robust groundwork for using the ISM to solve the problems (1)-(4).

Let the function $u_0(x)$ be given, satisfying the condition (3). Then the solution to the problem (1)-(4) is found using the following algorithm.

- Solve the direct scattering problem with initial function $u_0(x)$, obtaining scattering data

$$\{r^+(\mathbf{c}, 0), \mathbf{c} \in \mathbf{R}; \quad \mathbf{c}_k(0), \text{Im } \mathbf{c}_k > 0; \quad \mathbf{C}_k(0), k = \overline{1, N}\}$$

for the operator $\mathbf{L}(0)$.

- Determine the time-evolved scattering data for $t > 0$, using Theorem 3:

$$\{r^+(\mathbf{c}, t), \mathbf{c} \in \mathbf{R}; \quad \mathbf{c}_k(t), \text{Im } \mathbf{c}_k(t) > 0; \quad \mathbf{C}_k(t), k = \overline{1, N}\}.$$

- Solve the inverse scattering problem using the Gelfand-Levitant-Marchenko integral equation method. Namely, restore the unique (by Theorem 2) solution $u(x,t)$ from the scattering data obtained in the previous step for $t > 0$.

Example. Consider the following problem:

$$u_t + t^3(30u^4u_x + 10u_x^3 + 40uu_xu_{xx} + 10u^2u_{xxx} + u_{xxxx}) + 6u^2u_x + u_{xxx} + \frac{1}{1+t^2}u_x = 0,$$

$$u(x,0) = -\frac{2}{\cosh 2x}.$$

The solution to this Cauchy problem is as follows:

$$u(x,t) = -\frac{2}{\cosh(2x - 8t^4 - 2 \arctan t)}.$$

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